

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 18

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First version of back-end drivers

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List of Acronyms

- API** Application Programming Interface
- DIAS** Data and Information Access Service
- EO** Earth Observation
- ESA** European Space Agency
- GDAL** Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
- OGC** Open Geospatial Consortium
- OSGEO** Open Source Geospatial Foundation
- PB** Petabyte
- REST** Representational State Transfer
- STAC** SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
- UDF** User Defined Function
- WPS** Web Coverage Processing Service
- WCS** Web Coverage Service

1 Overview

This deliverable, which is accompanied by two other project reports (D17: openEO full API implementation, first version; D20: First versions of three front-end drivers) describes the status of different back-end drivers supporting the first version (v0.4.x) of the openEO API (D17). As of July 2019, seven back-ends are in active development, five of which have publicly deployed their implementation of the openEO API. The online back-ends provide up to tens of unique data collections and support an extended selection of processes for users to work with. The services and processes offered by each back end are presented in section 3 and 4, respectively.

2 Back-end drivers

The following back-end drivers currently support openEO v0.4.x:

- **VITO GeoPySpark**

api: <http://openeo.vgt.vito.be/openeo/0.4.0>

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-geopyspark-driver>

GeoTrellis¹ is an open source Scala library that facilitates fast operations on raster data using Scala and Apache Spark. It enables distributed computing on large data sets using map algebra techniques and supports vector, raster and point cloud data. GeoTrellis provides RESTful openEO endpoints and raster processing at web speeds (sub-second or less). The driver implements a direct (non-REST) version of the openEO client API on top of GeoPySpark. The back-end has been tested with Spark on a Yarn cluster and with Apache Accumulo as the tile storage back-end for Geotrellis. The openEO driver could, with minor modifications, be adapted to work with other Geotrellis back-ends, such as S3.

- **Mundialis GRASS/Actinia**

api: <https://openeo.mundialis.de>

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-grassgis-driver/tree/openeo-api-0.4.0>

The GRASS GIS driver implements the openEO Core API interface for the GRASS GIS² as a Service (Actinia Core; available from https://github.com/mundialis/actinia_core) - a software solution for parallel, large scale geodata processing. It is a highly scalable REST interface to process geodata with the GRASS GIS in a distributed environment. GRASS GIS is a free and open source software package providing geospatial processing engines in a single integrated environment for raster, vector, and 3d-voxel processing as well as image processing capabilities [1].

- **EODC**

api: <https://openeo.eodc.eu>

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-openshift-driver/tree/0.4>

The EODC driver is composed of a combination of frameworks, all Python based. The

¹<https://geotrellis.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²https://live.osgeo.org/en/overview/grass_overview.html

current solution is tailored to work with a file-based multi-PB storage of Sentinel Level 1 data, stored in their original compressed format. The API is built with Flask/Nameko and connected to a Celery cluster orchestrated by the Airflow task scheduler. Jobs are executed on the cluster's workers using an in-house Python package (eoDataReaders), based on OSGEO's GDAL. The whole setup is dockerized.

- **WWU Google Earth Engine**

api: <https://earthengine.openeo.org>

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-earthengine-driver>

The openEO Google Earth Engine Driver is a facade to the Google Earth Engine API. It is a nodeJS-based server implementation that implements the openEO API and translates incoming process graphs into corresponding requests to the Google Earth Engine JavaScript API. Google Earth Engine as such works mostly on images and image collections, which is a contrast to openEO's data cube view. Therefore, the openEO driver internally manages a virtual data cube with metadata that is required to offer a data cube view on top of Google datamodel.

- **Sinergise / Sentinel Hub**

api: no public deployment yet

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-sentinelhub-driver>

Sentinel Hub³ is a service-oriented platform that aims to facilitate processing and exploitation of satellite imagery by providing efficient access to several Earth observation data sets via easy-to-integrate web services. The main features of the system are: automated archiving process, ensuring that data are always synchronised with official sources; full resolution access over web services, with automatic re-projection, mosaicking, ortho-rectification and other standard processing; user-defined scripts to define spectral band expressions and other remote sensing products; multi-temporal processing for on-the-fly computation of user-defined algorithms on time-series; service for statistical analysis of a time-series over an area or point of choice; and APIs for advanced feature integration. Sentinel Hub works with original EO data, avoiding intensive pre-processing and additional storage for processed tiles. Some of the data accessible through Sentinel Hub are stored as AWS Public Datasets⁴ (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Landsat 8, MODIS) and some are hosted on CloudFerro EO Cloud⁵ (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, ENVISAT, ESA's archive of Landsat 5, 7 and 8) [2]. The developed driver adds support for openEO operations with the data obtained from Sentinel Hub.

- **JRC / JEODPP**

api: no public deployment yet

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-jeodpp-driver>

The JEODPP architecture consists of processing servers accessing the data provided by a series of storage servers and their directly attached storage in a distributed file system environment orchestrated by a management and meta data server mapping the logical file names and paths to their physical location. The I/O bottleneck typically observed with

³<https://www.sentinel-hub.com>

⁴<https://aws.amazon.com/earth/>

⁵<https://finder.eocloud.eu/>

network attached storage is avoided by considering appropriate high speed server inter-communication topology. This topology has the best scalability compared to arbitrated loop and point-to-point alternatives.

- **EURAC / WCPS**

api: <https://openeo.eurac.edu>

repository: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-wcps-driver/tree/0.4.0>

Web Coverage Service (WCS) is an interface standard by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) that supports the retrieval of geospatial data as coverages representing space and time-varying phenomena. The coverage data of a WCS is returned in forms that are useful for client-side rendering, as input into scientific models, and for other clients [3]. The Web Coverage Processing Service (WPS) extends this standard by defining a language that is capable of processing and retrieval of multi-dimensional geospatial coverages that represent images, sensor observations or statistical data. The WCPS language is independent from any particular request and response encoding, as no concrete request/response protocol is specified by the standard. For setting up a WCPS instance, therefore, a separate, additional specification establishing the concrete protocol is required. This allows embedding of WCPS into different target service frameworks [4]. The openEO WCPS driver is built on top of rasdaman ("raster data manager"), an Array Database that allows the storing and querying of multi-dimensional arrays. Rasdaman can process arrays residing in file system directories as well as in databases. The developed driver itself however is operational with all WCPS compliant web services and translates openEO process graphs into WCPS queries for generation of results.

3 Implemented services

The back-ends listed in Section 2 are in active development and they are at different stages towards being fully compliant with the openEO API v0.4.x specification (D17). The aim of this section is to briefly describe their capabilities and their compliance to the specification.

Table 3.1 lists the services defined in the API specification, and summarises which ones are implemented by the different back-ends, providing an overview of their capabilities. Efforts to fully validate back-ends (i.e. running compliance tests to verify the existence, functionality and response of endpoints) resulted in two tools (<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-backend-validator>) written in Python and Go, respectively. However they are not yet mature enough and the list in Table 3.1 is based on the endpoints listed under the "/" endpoint of each back-end. Nevertheless, the table provides insight on the general functionalities implemented.

All back-ends provide information on collections and processes available, and three (EODC, WWU/GEE, EURAC/WCPS) have implemented the STAC specification for metadata (<https://github.com/radiantearth/stac-spec>). All back-ends provide functionalities to store process graphs and process jobs. The EODC and WWU/GEE back-ends implemented File Management services for upload/download of user files. The EODC is the only one to have implemented authentication with OpenID Connect, while the VITO back-end is the only one to offer

an additional service, namely a WMTS.

	VITO	Mundialis	EODC	WWU/GEE	EURAC	Sinergise	JEODPP
API Discovery	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially
Data Discovery	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Process Discovery	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially
Auth. (OpenID Connect)	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Auth. (HTTP Basic)	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Batch Processing	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	No	Partially
Synchronous Processing	Yes	Outdated	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
Secondary Web Services	Partially	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
Estimate Processing Costs	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
File Management	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Process Graph Management	No	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Partially	Partially
Process Graph Validation	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
User Defined Functions	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Subscriptions	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No

Table 3.1: Endpoints of the openEO API implemented at different back-ends.

The following list gives overview about which API endpoints must be implemented to be fully compatible:

- API Discovery: GET /, GET /.well-known/openeo, GET /output_formats
- Data Discovery: GET /collections, GET /collections/collection_id
- Process Discovery: GET /processes
- Authentication (OpenID Connect): GET /credentials/oidc
- Authentication (HTTP Basic): GET /credentials/basic
- Batch processing: GET & POST /jobs, GET & DELETE /jobs/job_id, GET & POST /jobs/job_id/results
- Synchronous Processing: POST /result
- Secondary Web Services: GET & POST /services, GET & DELETE /services/service_id
- Estimate Processing Costs: GET /jobs/job_id/estimate
- File Management: GET /files/user_id, GET & PUT & DELETE /files/user_id/path
- Process Graph Management: GET & POST /process_graphs, GET & DELETE /process_graphs/process_graph_id
- Process Graph Validation: POST /validation
- User Defined Functions: GET /udf_runtimes
- Notifications and Monitoring: GET /subscriptions and at least one topic from the Subscriptions API

4 Implemented processes

Deliverable D15 listed more than 100 processes that back-ends are recommended to implement. The selection was driven in the first place by the use cases and aimed at providing broad functionalities for manipulating as well as processing data cubes. Furthermore, the processes specification offers flexibility, since the API allows custom processes to be defined according to a common framework.

This section summarises the processes implemented by each back-end.

4.1 VITO GeoPySpark

The VITO GeoPySpark back-end provides 39 processes, 6 of which are custom (underlined):

absolute, aggregate_polygon, aggregate_temporal, and, apply, apply_dimension, apply_pixel, apply_tiles, ceil, cos, eq, filter_bands, filter_bbox, filter_daterange, filter_temporal, floor, get_collection, gt, gte, ln, load_collection, lt, lte, mask, mask_polygon, max, max_time, mean, min, min_time, not, or, reduce, reduce_time, run_udf, save_result, sin, variance, zonal_statistics

Furthermore, the back-end supports the use of User Defined Functions (UDFs).

4.2 Mundialis GRASS/Actinia

The Mundialis GRASS/Actinia back-end provides the following processes, 7 of which are custom (underlined):

NDVI, bbox_from_raster, filter_bbox, filter_daterange, get_data, map_algebra, raster_exporter, reduce_time, rgb_raster_exporter, temporal_algebra, zonal_statistics

4.3 EODC

The EODC back-end internally supports most of the processes defined in D15, including all the processes under the tags "arrays", "comparison", "masks", "math", "reducer", "sorting", "texts" and "vegetation indices", most of the ones under the tags "filter" and "import" and some of the processes tagged as "cubes". However not all of them are yet available under /processes since they are currently under test. Furthermore, the back-end is not yet optimized, particularly for n-ry processes.

4.4 WWU Google Earth Engine

The WWU GEE back-end provides 45 processes, all of which are defined in D15:

absolute, add_dimension, apply, apply_dimension, arccos, arcsin, arctan, ceil, cos, cosh, e, exp, filter_bands, filter_bbox, filter_polygon, filter_temporal, first, floor, int, last, linear_scale_

D18: 1st version of back-end drivers

range, ln, load_collection, max, mean, median, min, normalized_difference, pi, power, reduce, rename_dimension, round, run_process_graph, save_result, sd, sin, sinh, sum, tan, tanh, text_begins, text_contains, text_ends, variance

4.5 Eurac WC(P)S

The EURAC WC(P)S back-end provides the following processes, 3 of which are custom (underlined):

ndvi, filter_bbox, filter_daterange, load_collection, save_result, max_time, min_time, stretch_colors

4.6 JEODPP

The JEODPP back-end currently provides the following processes:

get_collection, load_collection, filter_bbox, filter_daterange, filter_bands, filter_temporal, ndvi, aggregate_polygon, reduce_time, save_result

4.7 Sinergise

The Sinergise back-end currently provides the following processes:

filter_bbox, filter_daterange, ndvi, min_time, max_time

5 Standardisation and templates

In order to simplify the uptake of the openEO API, project partners are (i) developing their API implementations open source and (ii) sharing common functionalities when possible. A common step to all back-ends is to parse the process graph (and processes defined in it), and translate it from the syntax defined by openEO to the syntax needed by the framework used to perform the computation. While the latter is typically specific to each back-end, the parsing step is common and the same software may be re-used by multiple back-ends (sharing the same programming language). Currently, multiple process graph parsers exist for Python, Java, JavaScript⁶ and new groups are encouraged to use/modify existing ones. However for Python three versions exist already, independently developed by different partners and it is planned to coordinate these efforts in the future.

Here is an example of the functionality of a Python process graph parser⁷, transforming the process graph from its original json format (openEO syntax) to a Python object which can be traversed by node or dependency (see below). This object can be used to further translate the

⁶<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-js-commons>

⁷<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-pg-parser-python>

openEO syntax to the back-end specific syntax for the computation. The translation of each process then depends on the computing framework implemented at the back-end.

JSON process graph:

```
{
  "s2a": {
    "process_id": "load_collection",
    "process_description": "Loading S2A data.",
    "arguments": {
      "id": "s2a_prd_msil1c",
      "spatial_extent": {
        "north": 48.40,
        "south": 47.90,
        "east": 16.84,
        "west": 15.96
      },
      "temporal_extent": ["2017-09-05", "2017-10-01"]
    }
  },
  "ndvi": {
    "process_id": "ndvi",
    "process_description": "Calculate NDVI.",
    "arguments": {
      "data": {"from_node": "s2a"},
      "name": "ndvi"
    }
  },
  "min_time": {
    "process_id": "reduce",
    "process_description": "Take the minimum value in the time series.",
    "arguments": {
      "data": {"from_node": "ndvi"},
      "dimension": "temporal",
      "reducer": {
        "callback": {
          "process_id": "min",
          "process_description": "Calculate minimum",
          "arguments": {
            "data": {"from_argument": "data"}
          }
        },
        "result": true
      }
    }
  }
},
```

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```
"output": {
  "process_id": "save_result",
  "description": "Save to disk",
  "arguments": {
    "data": {"from_node": "min_time"},
    "format": "Gtiff"
  }
}
```

Traversable Python object. The nodes can be listed in order of dependencies (no dependency first) and the dependencies of each node can be queried.

Node ID: s2a_f3e021e07a69adee

Node Name: s2a

```
{'arguments': {'id': 's2a_prd_msil1c',
               'spatial_extent': {'east': 16.84,
                                   'north': 48.4,
                                   'south': 47.9,
                                   'west': 15.96},
               'temporal_extent': ['2017-09-05', '2017-10-01']},
 'process_description': 'Loading S2A data.',
 'process_id': 'load_collection'}
```

Node ID: ndvi_b44e3266ff088509

Node Name: ndvi

```
{'arguments': {'data': {'from_node': 's2a_f3e021e07a69adee'}, 'name': 'ndvi'},
 'process_description': 'Calculate NDVI.',
 'process_id': 'ndvi'}
```

Node ID: min_time_ab371b3987c46138

Node Name: min_time

```
{'arguments': {'data': {'from_node': 'ndvi_b44e3266ff088509'},
               'dimension': 'temporal',
               'reducer': {'from_node': 'callback_1c228696f2072715'}},
 'process_description': 'Take the minimum value in the time series.',
 'process_id': 'reduce'}
```

Node ID: callback_1c228696f2072715

Node Name: callback

```
{'arguments': {'data': {'from_node': 'ndvi_b44e3266ff088509'}},
 'process_description': 'Calculate minimum',
 'process_id': 'min',
 'result': True}
```

Node ID: output_51b7ae67123af385

Node Name: output

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```
{'arguments': {'data': {'from_node': 'min_time_ab371b3987c46138'},  
              'format': 'Gtiff'},  
  'description': 'Save to disk',  
  'process_id': 'save_result'}
```

Furthermore, the consortium is also providing templates that can be used by new groups to deploy the openEO API on their data centres. For example, EODC developed a dockerized solution that can be deployed with a simple docker-compose (<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-openshift-driver/blob/0.4/docker-compose.yml>).

6 Connection to DIAS

To facilitate and standardise access to data, the European Commission has funded the deployment of five cloud-based platforms providing centralised access to Copernicus data and information, as well as to processing tools, namely the Data and Information Access Services (DIAS). Given the importance of these platforms for users, the openEO Consortium is striving to create a connection between them and the openEO API and related ongoing work is discussed in this section.

6.1 WEkEO DIAS

As of December 2018, EODC has been federated to the Copernicus DIAS WEkEO⁸. The two centres together provide a full archive of Sentinel 1-2-3 data, on top of additional datasets. The EODC implementation of openEO⁹ has therefore been set up on a virtual machine federated with the WEkEO DIAS and work is under way to create the related data catalogue needed to work with WEkEO's data. For this, EODC is setting up a docker solution that creates a CSW¹⁰ server where data can be ingested. This solution should be flexible enough to work on any file-based back-end.

6.2 Sobloo DIAS

VITO is currently testing to connect their infrastructure to Sobloo via the openEO syntax. This task is currently ongoing.

⁸https://www.wekeo.eu/dec_2018_update

⁹<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-openshift-driver/tree/0.4>

¹⁰https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Catalogue_Service_for_the_Web

7 References

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- [4] “OGC WCS OpenGIS Web Coverage Processing Service (WCPS) Language Interface Standard; 08-068r2.” [Online]. Available: <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wcps>

